

INFLUENCE OF ROUTINE INSPECTION ON SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY.

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Abstract

This paper highlights the influence of routine inspection on secondary school teacher's productivity. Attention is drawn to different types of inspection that can enhance teachers' effectiveness, example concept of inspection, purpose of inspection, full inspection, follow up inspection, brief visit inspection, special visit inspection, familiarization inspection and concept of teacher productivity. In this paper, it was clearly stated that government should imbibe the culture of inspection to enhance teachers' effectiveness and productivity. The paper recommends that teachers should be provided with relevant teaching and learning facilities which will consequently enhance their teaching and productivity.

Keywords: *Routine inspection, Teachers, Productivity.*

INTRODUCTION

In order to avoid anarchy or haphazard operation, every organization, formal or informal requires certain measures of control. Inspection is an integral part of school administration which is constantly used to describe a variety of behaviour been exquisite by divergent group of scholars-, within the content of specific academic environments.

As a formal organization, the school needs proper control if its set goals and objectives must be accomplished. Myers and Murphy (1998) defined control as the process of monitoring something, comparing it with some

Standard and them providing selective record adjustment.

Since education is regarded as the important instrument of socialization, development and integration, therefore, concerted efforts should always be made to ensure that the system is on course through effective routine inspection and monitoring. Besides, routine inspection of our schools especially secondary schools become more imperative now that the general public are clamouring for the improvement of our education system based on what they term as "falling standard of education".

Opadokun (2011) observed that schools are built or designed to bring about learning in public through the effort of teacher. The values of inspection lie on the development improvement of the teaching learning situation which is reflected in the development of the public. To, this end, the school environment and teacher should be constantly inspected to meet the approved standard needed for ' the achievement of educational goals.

Purpose of Inspection in Education

The flaws and ineffectiveness that plague the educational system today are the cumulative results of poor monitoring and inspections. There are various reasons for carrying out inspection in schools. Ogunsaju (2000) pointed out that one of the most crucial reasons is to ensure that teachers within the school system have been performing their duties for which they are appointed. Another cogent reason is to improve the productivity of teachers so that they contribute maximally to the attainment of the systems goals.

However, it was generally observed that for an inspector to achieve the stated purpose, it is necessary that the inspector has a clear understanding of how to go about achieving the purposes. An un-clear purpose or purposes will definitely become hazardous in the process of inspection. Other reasons for inspection of schools as stated by Ogunsaju (2000) are:-

- * To know the performance of the teachers recruited to teach in the

school system.

- * To determine whenever a teacher should be transferred promoted, retrained or dismissed.
- * To improve incompetence or to make competent.
- * To discover special abilities or qualities possessed by teachers in the schools.
- * To provide a guide for staff development.
- * To know the effectiveness of class room management by the teacher.
- * To know the direction of the school.
- * To assess the "tone" of the school and identify some of its most urgent needs.

Full Scale Inspection

Opadokun (2011) described this type of inspection as well planned, organized and comprehensive in the sense that it covers all aspects of the school both curriculum and co-curricular. It involves a team from the Ministry of Education with the leader co-coordinating the activities of other inspectors who inspect their respective area. This type of inspection lasts for about 2 to 5 days depending on the size of the school. The activities carried out in this type of inspection are; pre-operation and post- inspection conference.

Fadipe (2000) identified the purpose of full-scale inspection to include quality control for approval for any public examination and for grant aiding a school.

Follow-up Inspection

This is always done after full scale inspection so as to ensure that:

- * Inspectors familiarize themselves with the school environment to know the school problems as to help where possible.
- * **Recognition Inspection:** This is the type of inspection that is carried

on in schools especially the newly established ones. This is done in order to recommend those schools to the State or Federal Government for recognition and approval.

This normally happens after the school might have undergone several full scale inspections. If the school is able to meet up with the laid down standard, it will now be recognized and recommended to the State Government or the Federal Government for approval.

Brief Visit Inspection

As the name implies, brief visit inspection is an unscheduled visit by an inspector to a school. The inspector might just decide to visit the school on his way to somewhere else in order to know the problems of the school.

It might even be an event to see how the school is being run. Apart from the normal inspections, the commissioner or minister of education might decide to pay an un-scheduled visit to any school.

Special Visit Inspection

This type of inspection is also referred to as emergency inspection. It is carried out to investigate or see to emergency situations that might have developed in the school. For examples, when there is fire outbreak, flood disaster, riot, rain storm or any other form of disaster that are unexpected.

Familiarization Inspection

This type of inspection usually occurs when a new head of administration is being posted or appointed by Ministry of Education. This will afford the new helmsman the opportunity to go round and know the exact locations of the school to make him/ her familiar with the principal and other staff of the various schools under his/her ministry.

School Inspection and Its Implication on Teachers' Productivity

One can gather a lot of facts from this paper work. It was revealed that periodic inspections of secondary school would enhance teachers' work and productivity. .

Moreover, it can also be included that through routine inspection, government is kept informed of the problems facing secondary schools especially in the area of teaching, learning, and materials. Thus, such problems will be given adequate attention, consequently, secondary school teachers effectiveness will be enhanced.

Furthermore, routine inspection influences in no small measure teachers' educational development. This is because refresher courses in form of regular seminars, workshops and academic conferences, duty leave and in service training which promote teachers' efficiency and effectiveness will be made available to them since the government is already aware of the teachers' challenges.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that through routine inspection, teachers - principals working relationship will be greatly improved. This is because the inspector will be able to evaluate teachers' performance based on their assessment of such teachers rather than on principals recommendation which may not be the true reflection of the teachers' output.

Recommendations

Based on the reviewed work, the writer of this paper makes the following recommendations:

1. Teachers should be provided with relevant teaching and learning materials that will enhanced teaching and learning activities which will consequently enhance their teaching productivity.

2. Government should ensure that schools are frequently and periodically inspected. This will enable (government) to be aware of the various problem confronting our educational institutions with a view to providing solutions to them.
3. Teachers' welfare should be given great priority. This could be done in form of good and prompt payment of their salaries and other welfare packages that could enhance their teaching and productivity.
4. Government should ensure that secondary schools are properly and adequately funded. This is necessary because inadequate funding is responsible for poor state of schools with negative effects on teachers' productivity in schools.
5. Finally, government and other stakeholders in the field of education should ensure that infrastructural facilities such as chairs, benches, good school buildings are adequately provided in secondary schools since the physical environment of school serves as incentives to both the teachers and students.

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